

THE FUTURE OF GLOBAL ENGLISH

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Abstract: The use of English as a global language is believed to have various benefits for people worldwide, including its ability to serve as a means of communication, empowerment, and unity among diverse cultures. However, some scholars have expressed concerns about the potential negative impact of English on linguistic diversity. According to these scholars, the widespread use of English in the world has led to the loss and death of many minority native languages. To address these concerns, it is suggested that non-native speakers should develop their own culturally contextualized teaching materials in English and that English should share its role as a global language with other languages like Arabic, Spanish, Bahasa Indonesia, Mandarin, among others. This way, various forms of English can emerge globally.

Keywords: a global language, English, communication, linguistic diversity, transformation

Introduction

The reason why English is considered a global language is due to its significant number of native and non-native speakers, making it the only language in the world with this distinction. For a language to be deemed global, it must be extensively spoken and studied internationally, have a wide geographical distribution, and be used in international organizations. As a lingua franca, English facilitates communication between individuals from different linguistic backgrounds. With approximately 800 million to 1 billion native and non-native speakers, English holds great significance in today's world. It is already an official language in over 60 countries and continues to be the most commonly spoken language worldwide. In the past, Latin and French were widely spoken languages before English gained popularity. French even served as the lingua franca from the seventeenth century up until the mid-twentieth century until English took over as the dominant global language.

At present, English holds the top spot as the dominant language globally. However, this may not remain the case in the future as other languages like Chinese, Arabic, Spanish, Hindi and Urdu are gaining ground and technology is making it easier to support them. This means that English may find it difficult to maintain its dominance in new forms of computer-mediated communication such as social media platforms like Facebook.

Another factor that could impact the global status of English is China's increasing influence. As China continues to develop economically, it may also begin to exert greater cultural influence. Some scholars have even compared the Chinese language with English. There are concerns that over the next few decades, Chinese could potentially replace English as the dominant global language. However, this may not be a cause for concern, as Chinese is notoriously difficult to learn and many Asian countries have little interest in learning it due to political tensions.

In addition, the use of English as a means of communication across different countries is significant. It can contribute to better understanding and respect for individuals with diverse

backgrounds, such as varying languages, cultures, and lifestyles. Martin Luther King Jr. once said that people fear each other because they do not know each other, which can be solved through effective communication. Furthermore, according to Seidlhofer (2005), the use of English as a global language can highly reduce misunderstandings and misinterpretations between people.

Furthermore, according to Tsuda, the prevalence of English over other native tongues may lead to discrimination, inequality, and injustice among those who cannot speak or write it. For instance, job applicants are often required to have excellent English skills, which puts non-English speakers at a disadvantage. Additionally, approximately 86% of people worldwide learn English as a second language; those who are more proficient in English may be perceived as having higher status than those who speak their native language fluently. Indeed, English is often mandated as a compulsory subject in schools globally, and some countries encourage their citizens to learn English while discouraging them from learning their local languages.

Many consider the Internet to be the epitome of global English, as it is estimated that 80% of information stored in computers worldwide is in English. This trend has been propelled by the rapid growth of computer and internet usage, resulting in extensive networking and global interconnectivity. Live interaction among users has also blurred the line between archived and ephemeral copies of texts, prompting a reassessment of intellectual property rights concerning electronic texts. In addition, the Internet was initially developed as a means of communication among a select group of scholars across the globe, but it will now cater more towards local, cultural, and business needs. With the rise in its usage, we can anticipate an increase in the diversity of languages used on the web.

Conclusion

The emergence of English as a global language has brought about significant transformations and changes. It is predicted that English will adapt to new environments and face challenges from other languages such as Mandarin, Arabic, and Spanish. Additionally, there will be numerous varieties of English spoken worldwide, potentially outnumbering native speakers of British English. Despite these changes, it is believed that English will remain a global language in the future with different perspectives and variations. Therefore, people should not view English as a disadvantage but rather an opportunity for improvement. It is also important for individuals to promote and use their local languages to preserve them for future generations.

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